

DEVELOPMENT OF THE LEVEL OF PROFESSIONAL KNOWLEDGE OF FUTURE HISTORY TEACHERS

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10003321>

Abstract. *One of the important conditions for comprehensive development for future educators is that the development of their professional level of knowledge skills is currently one of the important tasks of pedagogical higher educational institutions. This article reflects on the requirements of future history teachers to effectively establish the development of the level of professional knowledge.*

Keywords: *innovative environment, integrated development, professional quality, dialectical development, the principle of historicism, development trends, methodological system, historical and cultural heritage.*

Today, maintaining the fundamentality of education, achieving modern quality on the basis of compliance with the current and prospective needs of the individual, society and state, is becoming a priority of the modern pedagogical community. It can be seen that the result of the quality of education is associated with the personality of the teacher, the need to constantly improve it, increase the level of professional knowledge.

The development of the teacher's level of professional knowledge is a holistic, multi-component personal and professionally significant process of the teacher's target activity in order to change the teacher's level of professional knowledge on his own, to consciously manage his professional development, to choose the goals, methods and means of professional self-improvement that contribute to the formation of an individual. The development of a professional level of knowledge helps to understand advanced experiences, their own independent activities, and is a means of self-knowledge and self-improvement.

In the reforms carried out in recent years in our republic, the legal framework for promoting the spiritual, intellectual, physical and moral maturation of future history teachers, ensuring open and high-quality education for young people, ensuring the perfect education of young people at all stages of education, supporting and encouraging talented and talented young people is being formed. In this regard, it is worth mentioning that the issues of methodological interpretation of the study of historical, spiritual, educational and pedagogical concepts and their implementation in the process of improving the educational system have been identified. On this basis, in the same globalization processes, it is necessary to determine the methods and possibilities of influencing the development of the socio-educational situation of future history teachers, and to study the specific peculiarities of the teaching profession and determine the factors determining the professional and personal orientation, the social needs of society and their compatibility with professional competencies. In this regard, history interprets the theory of teaching, the need to improve the mechanisms of activity, professional qualities, pedagogical-psychological abilities, creative, cognitive competence and competency development-based programmatic education, methodological system, innovative means of teaching, scientific-based literature of future history teachers.

Preparation for the development of the level of professional knowledge of future history teachers is carried out when certain external and internal conditions are created. One of the main external factors is the implementation of the preparatory process for the development of the professional level of knowledge of future history teachers on the basis of a clearly developed program, this program includes the following components:

- goal (development of the level of professional knowledge, in which future history teachers contribute to the creation of an individual style of professional activity and are a means of self-knowledge and professional self-improvement);
- content (formation of a system of professional knowledge that constitutes the level of professional knowledge of future history teachers, the development of future history teachers and the practical skills necessary for its implementation);
- organizational and activity (forms, methods and means of professional training aimed at increasing the level of preparation for the development of the level of professional knowledge of future history teachers);
- diagnostics (diagnostic complex future history degree of readiness for the development of the level of professional knowledge of teachers and author's program).

And the internal factor is the formation of the readiness of future history teachers to develop the level of professional knowledge. The criteria for the readiness of future history teachers to develop the level of professional knowledge are: the professional orientation of the individual, the ability to develop professional self, the development of reflex skills.

The level of professional knowledge of future history teachers should be built on the basis of the requirements for the training of a specialist. Such knowledge includes:

- knowledge of the national and cultural peculiarities of their country, the importance of their native language in the modern world, interpersonal and intercultural treatment and etiquette;
- knowledge of the “socio-cultural portrait”, symbols and cultural heritage of his country;
- knowledge of the realities of the existence of the land of oz, lifestyle, traditions, customs, main national peculiarities and etc.

Future history teachers, in accordance with the requirements of state standards and historical science programs, must have the following in accordance with the level of professional knowledge:

- description of the stages of national and world history, historical events, processes, phenomena of world and national history from ancient times to the present day;
- Explaining the peculiarities of socio-political, economic and socio-cultural development of Uzbekistan and countries of the world, the cultural diversity of humanity;
- assessment of historical events, religious phenomena in terms of their impact on milly and world history in different historical periods.

The future history teacher should master the socio-cultural content of the educational content in school history textbooks to the extent that it provides for the satisfaction of social needs for humanitarian knowledge. These needs include: ensuring a person's access to domestic and world culture, expanding his cultural world, mastering the historical and social experience accumulated by mankind, understanding the trends in the development of Man and society and the problems that arise in these cases. In a rapidly developing and rapidly changing world, the ability of a history teacher to master new layers of knowledge is one of the main professional

competencies. A history teacher must have the ability to manage information flows that contain public and political information.

The requirements for the professional training of future history teachers include:

- assimilation by Future History Teachers of knowledge about the laws of development of human society in the social, economic, political, spiritual and moral spheres from ancient times to the present day, the development of a problematic, dialectical understanding of history based on the generalization of factual, specific materials;

- development in future history teachers of the ability to understand processes, phenomena and events in their dynamics, interrelationships and interdependencies, based on the principles of scientific objectivity and historicism on the basis of historical analysis and a problematic approach;

- the formation of a system of social values among teachers of future history on the basis of an understanding of the legitimacy and progressiveness of Social Development and superiority over personal interests, an awareness of the possibility of revealing the uniqueness of each person only in society and through it;

- development of the ability to study and analyze sources of historical information, draw conclusions about their richness, significance;

- cross-referencing information from different sources and identifying common and different aspects, comparing different assumptions and assessments of historical events and individuals, identifying and substantiating their point of view, participating in discussions;

- to gain an active understanding of the historical and cultural heritage of their country and other countries of the world, the experience of striving to preserve and increase it.

In place of the conclusion, it is worth noting that the development of the level of professional knowledge of future history teachers depends on the study of the science of history closely linked to national cultural values, improvement in the direction of personal and professional socialization, modern requirements and the level of spiritual, cultural development of society. In the process of developing the level of professional knowledge of future history teachers, it is necessary to apply the practical skills of future history teachers in activities, develop their activity, reflect, expand their social knowledge and develop the field of social activity. On this basis, the formation of future history teachers as a multifaceted category of the development of the level of professional knowledge includes pedagogical, psychological, social and cultural components and assumes the organization of a separate educational process that has a complex impact on the personality of the future teacher.

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